

Владимирский государственный университет

**МОЛОДАЯ НАУКА
В СОВРЕМЕННОМ УНИВЕРСИТЕТЕ**

**МАТЕРИАЛЫ I ВСЕРОССИЙСКОЙ
НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЙ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ
С МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫМ УЧАСТИЕМ**

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Стрелов Сергей Максимович	
Культурные связи г. Владимира в XII веке с европейскими странами на примере памятников владими́ро-суздальской архитектуры (Успенского, Дмитриевского соборов и церкви рожества Богородицы в Боголюбове).....	140
Федина Карина Сергеевна	
Феномен метафоры в академических текстах, ее роль в восприятии текста....	144
Хрусталёва Юлия Сергеевна, Лезёва Татьяна Ивановна	
The history of graphic design as a means of visual communication	149
Шуева Анастасия Ивановна	
Selling headline language.....	157
<i>ВОПРОСЫ ЛИНГВИСТИКИ ТЕКСТА И ПЕРЕВОДА</i>	161
Анучина Дарья Алексеевна	
Описание сублингвистических идеограмм как языка комиксов на примере Batman / Superman: World's finest (2022), issue: 1	161
Бахриддинова Юлдузхон	
Lexicographic foundations of translation in computer linguistics.....	170
Власов Артем Алексеевич	
Similarities and differences of refereeing terminology in hockey and football (on the material of the english language).....	174
Глебова Яна Андреевна, Резниченко Евгения Олеговна	
Особенности молодежного жаргона и его влияние на французский язык	177
Дейнега Елена Алексеевна	
Сравнительный анализ характеристик письменных текстов экскурсий в русском и английском языках	183
Зубарева Анастасия Игоревна	
Особенности текстов гастрономического дискурса в немецком языке	188
Карачевцева Валерия Витальевна	
Употребление англицизмов в русском молодежном сленге.....	194
Котов Даниил Альбертович	
Субъект в дательном падеже в пассивных конструкциях немецкого языка.....	201

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LEXICOGRAPHIC FOUNDATIONS OF TRANSLATION IN COMPUTER LINGUISTICS

Abstract. In modern lexicography, it is difficult to imagine a project created by a dictionary only for publication on paper. The creation and editing of dictionaries is carried out using professional software (dictionary creation systems), ready-made dictionaries are published not only in paper form, but also in the format of online dictionaries, electronic and mobile dictionaries. New technologies for compiling and publishing dictionaries pose some difficulties for lexicographers. This article discusses the issues and problems of computer linguistics, its linguistic foundations, computer lexicography and translation in electronic dictionaries.

Key words: lexicography, dictionary types, software, electronic and mobile dictionaries, academic dictionary, linguistic data.

In the 21st century-the age of development of technology and science, not every sphere of society in the process of its development, of course, has no way to resort to the development of technology. Including modern linguistics is no exception. Focusing on the stage of historical development of linguistics, this period corresponds to the 50s of the XX century, that is, the processes of the emergence of computer linguistics and its study in linguistic experiments. The initial reason for the emergence and development of computer linguistics in linguistics is that humanity, living in the modern world, began to make visible advances in each area, and as such, various language barriers for exchanging information with each other and the problem of finding a solution to it arose between them.

As a solution to such problems, da in the 1950s, the creation of early electronic computers and its help achieved not only the translation of data from one language to another, but also mathematical computing, data storage and many other advantages. The first experiments on machine translation were conducted at Georgetown University (Washington, D.C., USA) in 1954.

After the rapid transition, research and development began aimed at creating machine translation systems (MT Systems) in industrialized countries of the

world. Although more than half a century has passed since then, the problem of machine translation is still not solved as much as necessary [Хорошилов 2006: 4].

Computational linguistics is considered as a discipline that develops linguistic problems of computerization.

Theoretical issues of computational linguistics are the subject of numerous studies of modern Russian science (Y. N. Karaulov, Y. N. Marchuk, B. Y. Gorodetsky, E. V. Vertel, O. A. Kazakevich, V. M. Andryushenko, V. V. Morkovkin, I. I. Ubin, L. L. Nelyubin, G. M. Mandrikova, etc.).

The first achievements in the field of automation of linguistic works penetrated, first of all, into lexicography, as a result of which a new direction was formed within the framework of this science - computer lexicography.

Thanks to the improvement of the tools of practical lexicography, the creators of dictionaries now have the opportunity to choose the form of the medium of their work: traditional "paper" or digital. When designing the glossary of phytonyms, the choice was made in favor of an electronic basis, which is due to objective reasons [Сивакова 2004: 9].

A text translation system, or machine translation, is another branch of software in computational linguistics that is designed and created for text translation, but the elements that need to be taken into account in machine translation are as important as non-machine translation. However, so far no machine translation system has been able to provide a completely error-free translation and they have never had a high quality translation. This question is related to the semantic aspects of human language and makes it more obvious the weaknesses of machine translation to choose the equivalent of quite correct options. Translation using a computer "Computer assisted translation" or abbreviated CAT, usually a professional level, is done using computer tools in order to increase the efficiency of the translation process. This translation is somewhat different from machine translation and is a human-made translation using computer tools, in fact, the best explanation for this type is a translation made by a human using a computer [Рахими 2015: 9].

The use of computer technology in linguistics is mainly served for the following areas: a) dealing with problems of machine translation; B) automation and compactification of vocabulary work; c) automatic search and processing of bibliographic data, etc. As a result of these works, a new direction in linguistics was born, called applied (applied) linguistics. In this direction, a large place is also allocated to computer linguistics. Major linguist I.V. Arnold believed that automation, collection, and processing of lexicographic information resulted in the development and publication of monolingual and multilingual dictionaries, glossaries, and a whole generation of concordances (dictionaries created by a single author) [Абдурахмонова 2018: 10].

According to famous lexicographer V. P. Berkov, dictionaries of the 21st century should have the following characteristics:

- large size;
- having a concentric structure;
- the fact that multiple dictionaries can be combined into one common dictionary;
- that dictionaries can be voiced;
- give full grammatical information about incoming and outgoing words;
- full disclosure of vocabulary;
- contains information about the systematic relationship of words; contains material with a graphic picture;
- reflects extensive material about related names;
- an "update service" is established that works continuously.

It can be seen from this that the creation process of electronic dictionaries is somewhat complex, and a simple book has many functions that it performs in relation to dictionaries, that is, most of the factors that a person performs are assigned to the computer and give rise to the rate of increase in work efficiency.

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ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ПЕРЕВОДА В КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

Аннотация. В современной лексикографии трудно представить проект, созданный словарем только для публикации на бумаге. Создание и редактирование словарей осуществляется с использованием профессионального программного обеспечения (системы создания словарей), готовые словари публикуются не только в бумажном виде, но и в формате онлайн-словарей, электронных и мобильных словарей. Новые технологии составления и публикации словарей создают определенные трудности для лексикографов. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы компьютерной лингвистики, ее лингвистические основы, компьютерная лексикография и перевод в электронных словарях.

Ключевые слова: лексикография, типы словарей, программное обеспечение, электронные и мобильные словари, академический словарь, лингвистические данные.